

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MUSIC THERAPY: A NEW ERA OF PERSONALIZED CARE AND SCALABLE IMPACTS

Inteligencia artificial en musicoterapia: una nueva era de atención personalizada e impactos escalables

Petra Kern, PhD, MT-BC, MTA, DMtG

Music Therapy Consulting

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5371-597X>

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Correspondence

petrakern@musictherapy.biz

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has quickly permeated various professional fields, including creative and therapeutic disciplines. In music therapy, AI provides tools that can augment traditional practices through enhanced workflows, creativity, personalized interventions, and data-driven insights. This article explores the potential of AI in music therapy, detailing its applications across planning, implementation, and evaluation phases. Trending AI technologies for generating text, images, music, and videos, that enrich therapy by tailoring interventions to diverse populations and individual client needs, are introduced. Selection criteria are outlined to guide music therapists in choosing appropriate tools for their practice. As an example, the e-book *Pippin the Piano* demonstrates how AI can generate valuable clinical resources. A field test highlights how the AI-generated materials complement telepractice through dynamic storytelling and interactive engagement while maintaining the therapist's central role in guiding therapy and building meaningful connections. Ultimately, AI holds significant promise for innovative therapeutic practices, but its integration requires digital skills, ethical awareness, and must adhere to professional standards. Therefore, an initial framework of core competencies is presented to guide music therapists in navigating these challenges. In conclusion, thoughtfully incorporating AI enables therapists to expand accessibility, inclusivity, and impact, while remaining competitive in an AI-driven job market.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, music therapy practice, personalized care

Resumen

La Inteligencia Artificial (IA) ha irrumpido rápidamente en diversos campos profesionales, incluyendo disciplinas creativas y terapéuticas. En la musicoterapia, la IA proporciona herramientas que complementan las prácticas tradicionales mediante la optimización de flujos de trabajo, el fomento de la creatividad, la personalización de intervenciones y el análisis basado en datos. Este artículo explora el potencial de la IA en la musicoterapia, detallando sus aplicaciones en las fases de planificación, implementación y evaluación. Se presentan tecnologías de IA emergentes para la generación de texto, imágenes, música y videos, las cuales enriquecen la terapia al adaptar las intervenciones a diversas poblaciones y necesidades individuales. Además, se describen criterios de selección para guiar a los musicoterapeutas en la elección de herramientas adecuadas para su práctica. Como ejemplo, el libro electrónico *Pippin the Piano* demuestra cómo la IA puede generar valiosos recursos clínicos. Un estudio de campo destaca cómo los materiales generados por IA complementan la telepráctica a través de narrativas dinámicas e interacciones participativas, preservando el rol central del terapeuta en la guía del proceso terapéutico y la construcción de conexiones significativas. En última instancia, la IA ofrece un gran potencial para prácticas terapéuticas innovadoras, pero su integración exige competencias digitales, conciencia ética y apego a estándares profesionales. Por ello, se presenta un marco inicial de competencias clave para orientar a los musicoterapeutas en estos desafíos. En conclusión, la integración reflexiva de la IA permite a los terapeutas ampliar la accesibilidad, la inclusividad y el impacto, al tiempo que se mantienen competitivos en un mercado laboral impulsado por la IA.

Palabras clave: inteligencia artificial, práctica de la musicoterapia, atención personalizada.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of artificial intelligence – from rules to creativity

Envision a world where machines compose music, craft poetry, and adapt to a person's unique ways of learning – all while enhancing the human experience. This is no longer science fiction but reality, thanks to Artificial Intelligence (AI). From its humble beginnings as systems designed to follow programmed rules, AI has transformed into a powerful force capable of simulating human-like intelligence. It learns from data, finds patterns, makes decisions, and performs actions, pushing the boundaries of what technology can achieve. The revolution began with “machine learning,” a breakthrough where AI systems no longer needed humans to hand-feed them rules. Instead, they began to train themselves, uncovering insights buried in massive datasets. Search engines like Google epitomize this leap, predicting individual needs and preferences with remarkable accuracy. Similarly, “adaptive learning systems” like Duolingo use AI to adjust lesson content in real-time, creating personalized educational experiences. But AI didn't stop there! With advances in “natural language processing (NLP),” machines began to understand, interpret, and even converse in human language. Tools like Siri and Alexa blurred the lines between assistant and companion, bringing conversational AI into everyday life. The most dramatic shift came in November 2022, when “generative AI” changed the game. Tools like ChatGPT and Google Bard (now Gemini) introduced the world to large language models (LLMs) that could generate human-like text, music, images, videos, and more, simply by learning patterns from data when specifically prompted by humans. Suddenly, AI was not just a tool – it became a collaborator, unlocking creative possibilities that seemed unimaginable just a few years ago (Kaul et al., 2020; Ruiz & Fusco, 2023; UNESCO, 2020; UTSouthwestern Medical Center, 2025).

ChatGPT, where GPT stands for “Generative Pre-trained Transformer,” is currently one of the most well-known examples of LLMs. But how does it work? Imagine asking, “Explain ChatGPT to a preschooler.” The model processes this prompt by breaking it down and analyzing the context based on everything it has learned from massive amounts of text data, such as books, websites, and articles. It then predicts the next words in the response to form a meaningful and coherent explanation, like this: “ChatGPT is like a robot that knows a lot of words and can talk to you. You ask it a question, and it tries its best to give you a smart answer.” However, the data LLMs are trained on is not perfect. It comes from publicly available sources, which means it might contain errors, outdated information, or even biases. These limitations can affect the quality and fairness of the model's responses. Additionally, LLMs don't “think” or “understand”

like humans—they predict words based on patterns, not personal experiences or reasoning. A simplified view of how ChatGPT improves its answers is through a process called reinforcement learning. For example, if multiple responses are generated to “Explain ChatGPT to a preschooler,” a system evaluates which answer is the most accurate and helpful. This feedback helps the model learn to create better responses in the future (Diaz, 2024; OpenAI, 2022; So, 2024).

Looking toward the future, “autonomous AI systems” (e.g., an automated agent) loom on the horizon, capable of autonomously adapting, improving, and functioning with minimal human input. While advancements hold immense potential for creative and therapeutic fields, their capabilities should always be used with care, especially in sensitive areas like healthcare, where accuracy, fairness, and context are essential. Yet, one thing is clear: AI is reshaping the way therapists work – leading in a new era of personalized care and scalable impacts.

AI in healthcare – transforming practice and efficiency

AI is becoming an integral part of medical healthcare, improving diagnostics, treatment strategies, and patient care. Its ability to analyze large datasets such as medical records, imaging studies, and laboratory results and identify intricate patterns enables physicians to make better-informed decisions and therefore improve patient outcomes. In addition, AI has the capability to empower patients through personalized health information, remote monitoring, virtual consultations, improved medication management, and increased transparency enabling earlier interventions, better health outcomes, enhanced patient engagement (Dave & Patel, 2023).

In psychiatry, the role of AI is increasingly promising by enhancing diagnostic accuracy, providing more personalized interventions, and improving accessibility, particularly for underserved populations. The American Psychological Association (APA, 2024) underscores the growing integration of AI-powered tools into clinical practice tasks like seamless patient intake, tailored treatment plans, tracking session data, patient monitoring, or comprehensive handouts. AI tools are transforming administrative workflows by generating progress notes, automating client reminders, and data-based reports, enabling clinicians to devote more time to direct patient interactions. LLMs and wearable technology are paving the way for automated interactive conversations and preliminary patient assessments for depression, suicide risk, and other issues (Abrams, 2025; Ly et al., 2017). While current iterations lack the clinical reasoning and empathy required for direct therapeutic interactions, future advancements may incorporate emotion recognition, personality assessments, and mental health risk detection. For instance, AI systems

may eventually analyze social media interactions or text exchanges to detect cognitive distortions and identify risks of mental health crises (Cheng et al., 2023).

Yet, the integration of AI into medical and mental healthcare is not without challenges. Ethical concerns surrounding data privacy, algorithmic bias, patient autonomy, and over-reliance on AI remain critical issues. It is essential to verify AI-generated content for clinical accuracy while addressing its limitations, such as contextual misunderstandings and occasional inaccuracies. Ensuring responsible and effective implementation requires careful evaluation and adherence to ethical guidelines (Abrams, 2024; APA, 2024a; Dave & Patel, 2023; Ly et al., 2017; Cheng et al., 2023).

AI in music therapy – bridging creativity and technology

While digital music technologies, assistive technologies, virtual and augmented reality tools are steadily advancing in varied music therapy settings (Partesotti & Magee, 2025; Swanson, 2023) the adoption and application of AI in music therapy practice is slowly emerging. However, AI-driven systems hold potential for cultivating greater accessibility, inclusivity, and equity in music therapy. Additionally, generative AI tools like ChatGPT have opened new avenues for enhanced creativity, personalized client engagement, and improved data-based progress tracking (Kern, 2023; Kern, 2024c).

As Geipel and Jordan (2024) reported in their exploratory self-study, ChatGPT can assist music therapists in songwriting, personalized fantasy stories, and generating playlists. Similarly, Stegemann and Weymann (2024) found in their brief survey potential applications of AI in reducing administrative tasks, generating playlists tailored to client's preferences, or analyzing clients' responses to music. Their preliminary findings, however, underscored concerns about ethical implications and training gaps, emphasizing the need for both comprehensive education and ethical frameworks in AI integration. Furthermore, Sun et al. (2024) highlighted that co-designing AI tools with music therapists could improve therapeutic outcomes by aligning applications with clinical goals, enhancing real-time feedback, and maintaining the human-centered values of therapy.

Despite these hurdles, AI in music therapy provides an untapped opportunity to complement the expertise of music therapists, serving as a bridge between human creativity and advanced technology. It can serve as a catalyst for innovation, create tailored content, streamline workflows, and allowing professionals more focus on client interaction, while

leveraging technology for support. By enabling adaptive interventions and providing data-driven insights, AI can empower music therapists to design more personalized and impactful therapeutic experiences. Figure 1 illustrates the integration of AI into music therapy practice within the broader context of healthcare.

Figure 1

AI in music therapy practice in context of healthcare

Note: This figure illustrates the relationship between AI in music therapy practice and the healthcare sector.

Prepared by the author.

APPLICATION OF AI IN MUSIC THERAPY PRACTICE

Tools for transforming care

AI tools have revolutionized the way professionals approach tasks across various domains, from writing and productivity to research, programming, and even lifestyle optimization. They can be accessed through many platforms (e.g., App Stores, Marketplaces) or found inside commonly used software (e.g., Canva with its AI-driven design features). For music therapists, these tools provide an opportunity to streamline workflows, enhance services, and ultimately elevate client care. However, with the exponential growth of AI-driven systems, choosing the right tools can be daunting. The rapid pace of development means therapists must evaluate tools thoughtfully to ensure they align with clinical needs and ethical standards.

Selecting the best AI tools requires more than just curiosity – it demands a clear understanding of the tool's capabilities and how it fits into therapeutic practice. Familiarity with AI platforms and identifying where they add value to therapy services takes time but is essential to ensure that their integration benefits both therapists and clients. By following the practical yet non-exhaustive guidelines, adapted from the American Psychological Association (2024b in Figure 2), music therapists can make well-informed decisions about selecting AI tools for their practice.

Figure 2
Selection criteria for AI tools

Note: This figure displays criteria for choosing effective and ethical sound AI tools for music therapy practice.

Adapted from APA (2024b) by the author.

Generative AI in music therapy

Integrating generative AI into music therapy practice offers new capabilities across key phases of practice: planning, implementing, and evaluating interventions. In recent years, AI tools have advanced significantly, enabling the creation of text, images, music, and video content from simple text prompts. Beyond text input, other prompt methods such as voice commands, scanned documents, existing music samples, and even client-generated artwork (OpenAI, 2025) can now be utilized to develop personalized, engaging, and accessible therapeutic materials. Whether streamlining administrative tasks, crafting a therapeutic song, designing visual aids, or generating customized music, these tools empower music therapists to enhance their sessions with innovative and client-preferred resources.

Table I
Trending AI tools enhancing music therapy practice

Tools (generating text, images, music, and videos)	Planning (producing input and ideas)	Implementing (offering personalized client engagement)	Evaluating (using data-based progress tracking)
Text (e.g., ChatGPT 4o, Gemini, Grok 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get summary information about diagnosis, assessment tools, or EBP interventions - Draft goals/objectives, intervention or session plans - Check equipment, materials, apps, or AI tools - Send automatic intake and consent forms or client reminders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Curate client-preferred music playlists - Write song lyrics and chord progressions - Create social stories - Apply language translation into clients' primary language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create evaluation forms - Generate progress notes - Send data-based reports - Turn reports or messages for clients into plain language
Image (e.g., DALL-E3, Canva-Dream Lab, Gemini image Gen 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design personalized visual schedules, or mood charts - Create visual supports for activities such as music-assisted relaxation or guided imagery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share imagery like conveying dreams or emotions - Create visual storyboards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use mood-tracking charts - Identify patterns in client's visual work
Music (e.g., MusicGen, Amber Music, AI AIVA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate copyright-free music - Create paced and timed music to guide movements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create client-preferred rhythm loops, soundtracks, or music compositions - Transform client-specific content into music 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use auditory tracking for client responses - Identify patterns in client's auditory work
Video (e.g., Powtoon imagine, Veo 2, Sora)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create engaging and personalized videos modeling examples for clients - Generate animated explainer videos or interactive learning models for caregivers - Produce multimedia-enriched videos for advocacy or marketing therapeutic services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use video during session to model behaviors or demonstrate step-by-step guides - Share explainer videos with caregivers and communities - Publish a marketing video on social media platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyze client behavior with video content - Identify patterns in client's facial expression

Note: This table presents AI tools designed to generate input and ideas, facilitate personalized client engagement, and support data-driven progress tracking throughout key phases of the therapeutic process (Kern, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c).

Table I presents trending generative AI tools for text, image, music, and video creation. These tools offer practical applications for generating input and ideas for session planning, personalized client engagement during session implementation, and data-based progress tracking for evaluation. While the list highlights tools used in the field, the rapid pace of AI

development means new tools are emerging regularly and likely are to be integrated into everyday software and services. Music therapists are encouraged to stay informed about the latest innovations and refer to the selection criteria when exploring new AI tools. Being open to technological advancements ensures music therapists can integrate the best tools into their practice, supporting meaningful and effective therapeutic outcomes.

AI project – *Pippin the Piano*

In early 2024, the e-book *Pippin the Piano* emerged as a creative exploration of the relevance, capacity, and functionality of popular AI tools, including ChatGPT, DALL · E, MusicGen, and Canva. The project utilized free versions of these tools available at the time to evaluate their potential for creating goal-oriented materials for clinical use with young children of various abilities. Inspired by the author's personal experience of relocating a childhood piano from Germany to Italy, the story weaves a cultural and musical adventure that concludes with a meaningful lesson and moral.

For clinical application, the e-book is supplemented with a detailed, music-mediated intervention guide outlining how each page of the book could be utilized in practice. The session framework includes age-appropriate music and movement activities that music therapists, early childhood educators, or parents can implement in diverse settings. The story is crafted to address three developmental goals:

1. Enhancing literacy skills (i.e., supporting vocabulary acquisition, comprehension, and story recall).
2. Facilitating narrative engagement (i.e., encouraging active participation and connection with the storyline).
3. Promoting cultural interest and imagination (i.e., inspiring curiosity about different cultures and fostering creative thinking).

Detailed objectives and measurement strategies as well as a documentation form make it easy for professionals to track children's individual progress towards these goals. The project development summarized in Table 2, outlines how common generative AI tools were integrated to generate text, images, and music.

Field test – Early childhood telepractice session

To evaluate the practical application of AI-generated music therapy resources, a telepractice session was conducted within an inclusive preschool classroom in North Carolina. The session involved five children and their classroom teacher, participating in a 30-minute online session delivered via Zoom.

Table 2
Steps and generative AI tools used to create Pippin the Piano

Steps	AI Tool	Content Description	Task or Sample Prompt
Idea Development	None (Author's Input)	Conceptualized storyline, designed music-mediated intervention, identified developmental areas and progress tracking.	- Develop a storyline about a piano's farewell in Germany, traveling through cultural adventures, and finding a new home.
Text Creation	ChatGPT	Generated text segments, refined language, session outline, goals/objectives, and evaluation forms.	- "Rewrite the following text in an engaging and child-friendly way."
Images Generation	DALL · E	Created unique watercolor-style illustrations for each scenario in the story.	- "Generate a watercolor image of a vintage Volkswagen bus in blue and gray driving through the Alps."
Music Creation	MusicGen	Produced copyright-free, culturally inspired music to accompany the story and session.	- "Create a traditional German folk dance tune from the Allgäu region with lively rhythms and cheerful melodies."
Video Production	Canva	Created animated multimedia slides for the e-book, translated it into German and Italian, and converted the e-book into multiple formats.	- Translate the e-book into German and Italian and convert each version into an autoplay MP4 video.
Approval and Refinement	None (Author's Input)	Validated the accuracy of AI-generated outputs and alignment with therapeutic goals and measurements, ensured cultural appropriateness, and mitigated biases.	- Review and adjust all content for quality, inclusivity and client-centered relevance.

Note: This table outlines the steps and generative AI tools used in developing the ebook *Pippin the Piano*, designed for early childhood music therapy practice. From Kern (2024d).

The e-book *Pippin the Piano* served as the central resource. The author facilitated the session by visually sharing the story illustrations created with DALL · E, narrating the text developed using ChatGPT, playing AI-composed music loops from MusicGen, while engaging the children through instrument play, vocal exploration, movement activities, and open-ended questions. The classroom teacher provided essential on-site support by modeling tasks, distributing instruments, assisting children with self-expression, and tracking their progress throughout the session.

Clinical observations revealed that all children participated actively in the session. Examples of engagement included joyful yodeling, flowing scarf movements, and rhythmic tapping to the AI-generated music. The children demonstrated emerging cultural awareness by asking questions such as, "Do you need to fly on an airplane to Italy?" and identifying another language when discussing the phrase, "Gute Reise, Pippin." While the children easily recalled the cow's name from the story, their comprehension of the broader narrative was less clear. However, repetition is a cornerstone of early learning, and the e-book allows educators to revisit the music-animated story in subsequent days. The early childhood educator provided positive feedback, noting: "I think the book is very interactive, and I love the sound effects that accompany the story. The explanation and teacher notes at the end are very helpful, although I did need to look up how to pronounce the region where the cows live. Lol."

This field test underscores the capability of AI-generated materials to enhance therapeutic sessions with dynamic, culturally engaging content, fostering meaningful interactions and measurable outcomes. Figure 3 features two QR codes: with AI-narrated autoplay video of the e-book, while the other provides a three-minute capture of the telepractice session, showcasing how the AI-generated resource was implemented in practice. Readers are encouraged to explore the session documentation form included in the e-book, which allows them to evaluate children's progress across the identified developmental goals.

Figure 3

Project: Pippin the Piano

Note: This figure includes QR codes linking to an autoplay video of the e-book and a telepractice session capture, illustrating the use of AI-generated materials in therapy. From Kern (2024d).

COMPETENCIES FOR MUSIC THERAPISTS IN AN AI-DRIVEN HEALTH SECTOR

Core competencies for navigating AI-enhanced therapeutic practices

As AI systems continue to shape healthcare and the job market, music therapists must be flexible and ready to acquire new skills to integrate AI technologies effectively into their practice. By gaining critical AI competencies, music therapists can effectively navigate an AI-driven health sector while maintaining the human-centered essence of their practice. The following list tailored to music therapists from various sources (e.g., APA 2024c; European Union, 2024; Kern, 2024a, b, c; UNESCO, 2024), outlines an initial framework of core competences essential for maintaining the therapeutic relationship, ensuring ethical AI application, and maximizing its potential to enhance care.

1. Digital Literacy and AI Familiarity

- Develop a clear understanding of the principles of artificial intelligence, including machine learning and natural language processing (NLP).
- Gain expertise in operating AI-powered tools and adaptive analytics platforms to enhance therapeutic practices.
- Stay informed about data privacy standards and implement cybersecurity measures to ensure safe navigation of AI systems.

2. Creative and Flexible Integration of AI

- Use accessible, inclusive, and culturally sensitive AI tools for creative tasks and adapt AI-generated outputs to client-specific needs, cultural context, and therapeutic goals.
- Incorporate AI technologies into hybrid therapy models and seamlessly blend traditional with digital services.
- Avoid over-reliance on AI to maintain the music therapist's role as the primary creative driver.

3. Data Analysis and Interpretation

- Analyze AI-generated data and identify patterns to track client progress.
- Interpret AI-generated data for personalizing interventions.
- Be cautious of biases inherent in AI data and ensure decisions prioritizing client well-being.

4. Ethical Considerations

- Apply established ethical guidelines and comply with country-specific regulations governing the use of AI in therapy.

- Safeguard client data by ensuring robust privacy protections and obtaining informed consent before incorporating AI tools into therapeutic practices.
- Identify and address biases in AI systems to ensure equity and inclusivity in their outputs and applications.
- Advocate for the transparent use of AI in music therapy and maintaining accountability for decisions influenced by AI systems.

5. Client-Centered Adaptability

- Maintain a strong human connection by balancing AI-driven efficiencies with empathetic and responsive care.
- Educate clients about the role of AI in music therapy and address any concerns they may have.
- Ensure clients retain agency and choice in their therapeutic process.

6. Time Management and Workflow Optimization

- Identify areas where AI can reduce workload and improve efficiency, enabling music therapists to focus on direct client care.
- Use AI to streamline administrative tasks such as scheduling, session notes, and documentation.
- Ensure that automation does not compromise the quality of music therapy services.

7. AI-Specific Training and Professional Development

- Stay informed on advancements in AI technologies relevant to music therapy.
- Learn to troubleshoot, adapt, and refine AI tools to optimize their therapeutic use.
- Collaborate with AI developers to provide feedback and improve tools tailored to music therapy.

8. Advocacy and Leadership

- Support music therapy within the context of an increasingly AI-driven healthcare sector.
- Advocate for accessible AI technologies that enhance inclusivity in music therapy settings.
- Shape policies and best practices for AI adoption in music therapy.

Emerging professional roles in AI-driven music therapy

The rise of AI and digital tools in music therapy has created a range of specialized roles that demand a blend of therapeutic expertise and technological proficiency. These roles provide novel opportunities for music therapists to expand their practice into innovative areas such as digital health, content creation, and remote therapy services. Table 3 highlights key job roles, responsibilities, and potential companies leading the evolution (Kern, 2024b). This preliminary information is designed to help music therapists confidently navigate the

growing digital job market in healthcare while aligning their skills with contemporary professional demands.

Table 3

New job opportunities in digital music therapy

Role	Task Description	Key Responsibilities	Potential Companies
Remote Music Therapy Services	Deliver music therapy sessions online, using AI to create personalized interventions and monitor client progress.	Conduct individual and group sessions, ensure client engagement, analyze progress using AI tools.	BetterHelp, TalkSpace, SimplePractice, Zoom, MusicTherapyEd, TheraNest
Tech Consulting for Music-Based Therapeutic Tools	Advising on digital tools for music therapy, including AI-powered applications.	Collaborate with developers, provide therapeutic insights, test AI-enhanced tools, and ensure usability and relevance.	Ableton, AUMI, SoundBeam, ChatGPT, LullaFeed, Digital Therapeutic Alliance, Apple
Research in Digital Therapy Innovations	Conduct studies to validate AI-powered digital tools and their impact on therapeutic outcomes.	Design research studies, analyze AI-generated data, and publish findings to inform evidence-based practices.	Berklee College of Music, Mayo Clinic, National Institutes of Health, JMIR Mental Health
Digital Health Content Creation	Create educational resources and tutorials integrating AI for client and therapist use.	Develop AI-driven interactive programs, write articles, and produce video tutorials for digital platforms.	Udemy, Coursera, Patreon, Skillshare
Advocacy and Policy Development	Advocate for the integration of AI-driven music therapy tools in healthcare policies and practices.	Collaborate with policymakers, develop guidelines for ethical AI use, and participate in advocacy groups.	Music & Memory, American Telemedicine Association, European Music Therapy Confederation
Digital Therapeutics Specialist	Integrate AI-driven therapeutic solutions into personalized patient care plans.	Implement AI-powered tools, collaborate with healthcare teams, monitor patient outcomes using digital metrics.	Music & Memory, Happify Health, Better Therapeutics, American Telemedicine Association

Note: This table highlights new opportunities for music therapists seeking to enter or expand their practice in an AI-driven healthcare sector.

From Kern (2024b).

CONCLUSION

AI in music therapy creates a unique intersection where human creativity and technological advancements come together to expand therapeutic possibilities. By thoughtfully embracing this technology, music therapists can enhance their practice with innovative tools while preserving the human-centered essence of their work. As AI continues to evolve, its integration must be guided by robust ethical frameworks and a unwavering commitment to the well-being of clients. Looking ahead, Artificial Intelligence in Music Therapy: A New Era of Personalized Care and Scalable Impacts signals a transformative development, where the boundaries of therapeutic innovation are limited only by imagination.

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